

**The Ontological Multiplicities: A Critical Reading of Tereza's Oneiric World
in Milan Kundera's *The Unbearable Lightness of Being***

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Abstract

The oneiric has always been conceived as an ontological realm opposite to the real world. In literature, the contents of dreams are generally analyzed through the lens of psychoanalytic methods. This paper attempts to understand the dimension of the real-oneiric dichotomy in Kundera, focusing on *The Unbearable Lightness of Being*. It argues that oneiric in Kundera is not a separate ontological area but rather one that leaks into the real and vice versa. By critically analyzing Tereza's series of dreams, the paper shows that Kundera gives an ontological and epistemological status to his oneiric by reassessing the imaginary and unconscious. The real and the oneiric coalesce organically, blurring the boundaries between them. The paper also looks at how, for Teresa, who dwells in the oneiric more frequently in the real world, the oneiric becomes a legitimate mode of her existence, as in the real world.

Keywords: Oneiric, real-dreamlike dichotomies, dream narration, ontology

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Oneiric: An Introduction

Oneiric has always been conceived as a separate ontological area in literature. Writers have always tended to posit it as an area that comes to life in a solipsistic state wherein the unconscious desires and repressed wishes always seek an outlet in the form of dreams. Since Freud, dreams have always been considered a solipsistic activity that negates the real world, where “the real world is replaced by an autonomous imaginary world free of external controls” (Morely 94). Novelists always imagine dreams as a phenomenon that unfolds in a realm cut off from the waking world, which for them is the real world, and it is against this world that they place the oneiric world. In Freud, the unconscious always derives from the conscious, waking mind, which feeds contents for the dreams in the body’s solipsistic state. Merleau Ponty, a phenomenologist, believes such a postulate is problematic because it reduces the unconscious to a secondary status and places the conscious over the unconscious. He uses the word ‘oneiric’ to address the unconscious or imaginary, which has always been considered a passive phenomenon in philosophy. He posits that the oneiric is very much a part of the waking world and not solipsistically disengaged from it. He problematizes the conscious-unconscious antithesis by positing the body, being-in-the-world, as the common ground in which both the real and imaginary occur. He even claims that our relation to others has an oneiric character.

Milan Kundera’s oneiric is somewhat similar to the one that Maurice Merleau-Ponty envisages. Unlike in Novalis and Kafka's novels, where dreams and reality fuse so well and give the readers a flight into a new space of otherwise impossible fantastic experiences, Kundera's oneiric world, at once questions and problematizes the very foundation of such spaces. While his thought of oneiric differs not drastically from his predecessors, his motive is not merely to posit the oneiric

against the real, phenomenal world and thereby summon the readers to a new terrain of experience. In *The Art of the Novel*, he expounds on oneiric: "Oneiric narrative, let's say, rather: imagination, freed from the control of reason and concern for verisimilitude, ventures into landscapes inaccessible to rational thought" (Kundera 81). He further states, "Like Kafka (and like Novalis), I feel that same desire to bring dream-dream imagination into the novel. My own way of doing it is not by a 'fusion of dream and reality' but by polyphonic confrontation" (Kundera 82). A critical scrutiny of his works would prove that it is not just a new narrative plane that he discovers with such a method, but also a possibility of reorienting what has been thought of dreams since time immemorial. Francois Ricard in his work *Agnes' Final Afternoon* observes that; "Instead of the customary literary uses for dreamlike tales—a prophetic or "psychoanalytic" use on the one hand, an ornamental one on the other—the Kunderian novel substitutes a purely aesthetic treatment: it is attached to the dream's content not as to the cause or the effect or the sign of something else, but for its own sake and for its own enigmatic beauty" (30). In Kundera, dreams are an aesthetic category as well as a narrative terrain where whatever happens in the real world has a resonance and impact. He does not conceive of the oneiric as an area where only the fantastical, surreal, and phantasmagorical events can unfold; on the contrary, he posits it as a terrain that is as normal and phenomenal as the real world, where the events unfold in a causal continuation of those of the real world. Further, by giving the oneiric a distinct ontology in his works, Kundera is able to problematize the 'real', which leaks so constantly into the oneiric. Marleau Ponty, in his *The Visible and the Invisible*, looks at the mutual reciprocity of the real and the oneiric; "The distinction between the real and the oneiric [dreamlike] cannot be identical with the simple distinction between consciousness filled with meaning and consciousness given up to its own void. The two modalities impinge on one another. Our waking relations with objects and others especially have

an oneiric character as a matter of principle: others are present to us in the way that dreams are" (Ponty 48). Also, more importantly, since the characters' existences and essence of their beings in the novel are mostly revealed in their experiences in the oneiric, the oneiric becomes the 'real' of many of his characters from an existential point of view. For example, although Chantal is apprehensive of the oneiric world in Kundera's *Identity* (1998), she frequents such a world and continually allows it to shape her sense of self. Surprisingly, the novel ends with the quandary of which is real and which is oneiric. Kundera's other novels, including *Ignorance* and *Life is Elsewhere*, also discuss the real-oneiric dichotomy. In *Ignorance*, Irene, an immigrant from Czechoslovakia living in Paris, always has dreams that are extensions of her thoughts in the real world. Her dreams show the images of her grand return to her home country, her favorite landscapes, and her reunion with her people. Although these images appear in dreams, they are thoughts that concern her the most in real life, and hence, they cannot be said to have come solely from the world of oneiric. In *Life is Elsewhere* (1974), Kundera invents a character named Xavier (the protagonist's alter ego, Jarmoil) and recounts his adventures in lucid, dreamlike episodes. Like Jarmoil and Xavier, the real and oneiric merge, and the novelist leaves it to the readers to decide which is real and which is oneiric. Interestingly, in Kundera's works, the transition from the conscious state to the oneiric happens not only when the characters are in the somnolent state but also when the to-and-fro movement from the real to the oneiric and vice versa is continuous. What is remarkable about this flow or leak is that the temporality and spatiality of the events that happen in the real are more or less the same when they slip into the oneiric, and one can but wonder whether what they are experiencing at the moment is real or oneiric. Paul Ricard observes this relationship: "This equality of two ontological areas—dream and 'reality' permits diverse relations between them, from their sharp separation to forms of reconciliation that make them practically

indistinguishable from each other" (Ricard 108). Interestingly enough, the oneiric becomes a more comfortable terrain for the characters than the real because it opens up infinite possibilities; to find answers to the puzzling questions they are not strong enough to express in the real, and to eventually find the essence of their existence. Interestingly, the weak and the downtrodden often occupy the oneiric in the Kunderian novels. This is no surprise, given their chaotic existence in the real. Nonetheless, it is not purely the 'unconscious' that speaks or appears in the oneiric but sometimes the waking mind, too. This is a very complex realm because the characters are 'not awake but aware' of what is happening in their oneiric, and hence, sleep in Kundera cannot be seen as just as a solipsist activity but as a phenomenon where the waking mind or the conscious world is not entirely cut off from the chain of events that happen in the oneiric. What is more interesting here is that it is mostly the characters' worries, apprehensions, and insecurities concerning their body, love, and relationships that appear in the oneiric. Most characters have a dreamlike being or existence and are seen more frequently in the oneiric than in the real world.

Tereza's Dreams: The Real and the Oneiric

For Kundera, characters are always born out of, not in, the abstracto, but of situations. The characters of *The Unbearable Lightness of Being* "were not born of a mother's womb; they were all born of a stimulating phrase or two or from a basic situation...Tereza was born of the rumbling of a stomach" (Kundera 37). This rumbling of the stomach is suggestive of the dilemma of the irreconcilable duality of body and soul that Tereza has been painfully concerned about since her childhood; her mother would always walk naked in the house and often ridicule her for her small breasts. She would never allow Tereza to lock the bathroom door. She would indirectly tell her daughter that her body is not unique, as there are millions of other bodies in the world that look

like hers, and hence, hiding such a body that has no distinct identity and existence is futile and pointless. Tereza, unfortunately, had no idea about the anatomy or biology of her body. "She can't reconcile herself to the idea that the human body pisses and farts" (Kundera 43). She tried to see herself through her body and often looked at the mirror to experience the amazement of seeing her own I. Having thus been compared to millions of bodies by her mother, Tereza desperately wishes to be unlike other bodies, but the resemblance to her mother shatters all her hopes of escaping the concentration camp of identical bodies. It is such an escape that leads to her meeting with Tomas, the protagonist of the novel. Tereza's first meeting with Tomas is purely a coincidence, a play of fortuities. She comes to him with a heavy suitcase containing the indelible marks of atrocities that her body had received from her family, especially from her mother; among the terrible consequences of those atrocities that were committed to her body, the following are the ones that Tereza is most concerned about; (1) She can no longer look at herself, at her body through the mirror, for what she might see is not the unique herself or I but rather a multitude of identical bodies, (2) She can no longer be herself or at least be different from her mother because she takes after her mother, (3) the image she had of herself, of her body and soul can now only be a world on the other side, the world she longed for. Teresa's body is, therefore, a body that strives for another world, a body that carries pain within. It is with such a heaviness that Tereza walks into Tomas's life of lightness, wherein he revels in womanizing and erotic adventures.

Tereza's entry into Tomas's life is somewhat dreamlike. "She seemed a child to him, a child someone had put in a bulrush basket daubed with pitch and sent downstream for Tomas to fetch at the river bank of his bed" (Kundera 6). This image or the metaphor of a child floating on the river in a basket has a surreal or oneiric shade about it, and this dreamlike trait or oneiric aspect can be later seen to reveal the essence of Tereza's character, who regularly dreams as well as narrates

them to Tomas. For Tomas, who is so touched by the innocent image of the child in the basket, Tereza feels like someone who "...had been with him for many years and was dying" (Kundera 7). Although she initially appears to him as someone who has just snapped out of a dream and come down to him, later, as he spends more time with her in intimacy, he realizes that her real world is somewhere between the real and the oneiric. Tomas is an insomniac and has difficulty sleeping close to another person. At first, it seems to him that Teresa's quick access to the world of sleep would help Tomas continue his amorous adventures with other women. However, Tomas is soon proven wrong because Tereza is endowed with the ability to be aware of what happens around her, even in her sleep, and quickly return from the antechamber of dreams. Just as she can doze off or sleep at the moment Tomas chooses, Tereza can also wake up anytime, no matter how deeply she has fallen asleep. This act of being aware and dreaming in Tereza has a phenomenological dimension. Merleau Ponty, in his *Phenomenology of Perception*, explains this phenomenon. "Though it is indeed from the dreamer that I was last night that I require an account of the dream, the dreamer himself offers no account, and the person who does so is awake. Bereft of the waking state, dreams would be no more than instantaneous modulations, and so would not even exist for us" (Ponty 293). He further notes that a dream is only present for the one who recalls it awake. Whether awake or asleep, the subject is always about the world. Even those dreams that visit her in her deepest sleep, Tereza can recall them as well as narrate them vividly and vehemently to Tomas, whose compulsive womanizing is always the stimulus behind such dreams.

Tereza's relation to Tomas is oneiric. Between them, the liveliest place is the oneiric; in this terrain, the most important events and exchanges of their life occur. Dreams are not a "secondary or degraded perception, a mere representation of something separate or external to itself" (Morely 93). Their oneiric and real are imperceptibly aligned and present them with experiences of all

nature. Tereza dwells in the oneiric for more extended periods than in the real, which is no surprise considering that her existence is full of heaviness and weakness. There are so many unspoken apprehensions, agonies, and complaints lying inside her, which the author presents to her in the oneiric as a series of dreams. Interestingly, although the contents of such dreams are unpleasant, Tereza never hesitates to narrate and share them with Tomas. The impulses behind Tereza's dreams are always jealousy and the fear she feels about Tomas's erotic adventures with various mistresses. Her first dream, wherein she sees cats (which in Czech slang means "pretty women") clawing at her face and body, shows us her insecurity and jealousy about her man's perpetual philandering. Throughout her marital life with Tomas, she has a series of dreams involving violence and horror, especially those involving nudity, execution, death, shooting, etc. "Her dreams recurred like themes and variations of television series" (Kundera 17). After she goes through Tomas' letters from Sabina, his mistress, Tereza has a dream in which Tomas orders her to watch from a corner while he and Sabina make love (Kundera 16). While this dream evidently comes out from Tereza's insecurity and possessiveness, what is striking here is the smooth transition or movement from the real to the oneiric realm. What is interesting about this dream is that we are unsure whether Tereza had seen this seen or not. This confusion is caused by the pace at which a painful experience in the real world for Teresa travels into the oneiric for a fuller and better unfolding. One dream of Tereza that is most alarming and visits her twice is, "I was at a large indoor swimming pool. There were about twenty of us. All women. We were naked and had to march around the pool. There was a basket hanging from the ceiling and a man standing in the basket. The man wore a broad-rimmed hat shading his face, but I could see it was you...The pool was full of corpses floating below the surface. And I knew I lacked the strength to do the knee bend, and you were going to shoot me. In a third cycle, she was dead" (Kundera 17). It is evident that this dream has its source in the feeling

of insecurity and pain she feels about Tomas' liaisons with other women. Teresa realizes that for Tomas, she is among the many bodies he engages in his carnival of erotic life, and that she will never be able to dissuade him from his pursuits, as it has become pathological. What is even odder about this dream is that Tereza shows no hesitation to narrate this dream to Tomas, in which the heinous violence is committed not by anyone else but Tomas himself. This narration shakes Tomas because the events she saw happened in the oneiric and not in the real world; hence, Tomas cannot blame Tereza for portraying him as brutal and heinous. By constantly narrating her dream experiences with Tomas, Tereza establishes an oneiric character in her relationship with Tomas. Gradually, the relation hierarchy between real and imaginary experiences collapses, and we slowly understand that for Tereza, a dream is a particular mode of existence. In all her dreams, Tomas' presence is felt directly or indirectly. Oddly enough, both in the real and the oneiric, he is the one who brings her agony and sorrow. By creating dreams wherein Tomas is always present, Kundera can be seen to challenge the conventions of psychoanalysis. The appearance or presence of the people we know in our dreams problematizes the real and imaginary divisions prevalent in psychoanalytic traditions. In his book *Imagination and Its Pathologies*, James Morley says, "If others who are real are nonetheless present to us in the manner of dreams and myths, this itself is sufficient to undermine any attempt to dichotomize the real and imaginary" (Morley 45). In Tereza's dreams, she is always weak, and Tomas is the one who is always strong and the agent of all atrocities; she keeps on revisiting to her dreams "running through them in her mind, turning them into legends. Tomas lived under the hypnotic spell cast by the excruciating beauty of Tereza's dreams" (Kundera 55).

In another cycle of dreams, Tomas sends Tereza to be killed on Petrin Hill. She sees six men strolling along at a leisurely pace up the hill. Three of them are to be executed. We are not clear

why they are to be killed. They are all male. The other three men show scornful generosity. One of them, who has a rifle in his hand, waves at Tereza and asks her if she has come to Petrin Hill by choice or at someone's insistence. Tereza wants to say no to the question, but does not want to disappoint. She tells the man, "Yes, of course. It was my choice" (Kundera 143). The man carrying the rifle gives her a shocking revelation that those who usually climb the Petrin Hill come with the desire to die there. When the man asks her if she would like to go first, she says she would like to be last. In Petrin Hill, the people who come to embrace death can choose their own trees. Two of them eventually choose plane trees, but the third wanders on and on as he sees no tree worthy of dying on. When one of the assistants tries to blindfold her with a dark blue ribbon, she refuses and tells him that she wants to watch. What prompts her to say so is not her courage or determination but her desire to postpone her death. "Once her eyes were covered, she would be in death's antechamber, from which there was no return" (Kundera 145). She looks around to choose a tree and sees a flowering chestnut. She leans against its trunk and looks up at its shining leaves. She hears the bustle of the city, and when he raises his rifle, her courage slips away, and out of weakness and despair, she confesses, "but it wasn't my choice" (Kundera 145). The man immediately lowers his rifle as he has no power to kill someone who has come to the Petrin Hill to die on his/her own accord. Tereza turns her face to the bark of the tree and starts crying. The tree that gifts death becomes an intimate being all of sudden; "as if it were her long-lost father, a grandfather she had never known, a great-grandfather, a great-great grandfather, a hoary old man come to her from the depths of time to offer her his face in the form of rough tree bark" (Kundera 146). While walking down the hill, the thoughts of the man, the man who had the charge to shoot her but did not, come to her mind. She longs for such a man who would have mercy upon him because Tomas betrayed her by sending her to death. This dream series acquires significance

because the content or events that Tereza sees in the dream have not happened in real life, nor are they entirely distinct content that the oneiric creates. The content ostensibly shows how Tomas dismisses her body as well as herself from his life by engaging in several erotic relationships with other bodies. Ricard notes this coalescing of the oneiric and the real; "no matter how much the dreams bring up a world other than that of the "ordinary" reality in which the characters move—or how much they derive from that strangeness some essential part of their power of fascination—in Kundera's novels this other world never seems either more or less real, or more or less meaningful, than the first" (Ricard 106). For Tereza, who has reverence for her bodily self, Josef's erotic affairs give not only agony but also shock because she cannot bear the thought of her body being compared to other women's bodies.

What follows the dream series of Petron Hill in the novel is Tereza's going to the flat of the engineer, who has been luring her to do so. This is an important episode in the novel as it shows how Tereza finally conforms to Tomas's belief that love and sexuality have nothing in common. She believes that it is Tomas who is sending her to the flat of the engineer and facilitating their erotic union. Interestingly, in this episode, the Petrin Hill dream series flashes can be seen. Tereza knows that her act of going to the flat can cast on her the shadow of infidelity nonetheless; "She would not stay long; long enough for a cup of tea; long enough to feel what it was like to reach the very border of infidelity" (Kundera 147). She has decided how she will respond if the engineer makes an advance to put his arm around her and invite her for intimacy. "She would say, as she said to the man with the rifle on Petrin Hill, 'It wasn't my choice'" (Kundera 147). However, to her great surprise, when the engineer advances, she fails to resist herself and completely surrenders to the flames of passion. Her "soul for the first time saw the body as something other than the banal;

for the first time it looked on the body with fascination" (Kundera 150). However, later, as the lovemaking reaches its zenith, she realizes that she must not allow her body to be tainted by someone she neither knows nor wishes to know. She feels her soul has left its mark on her body; hence, she must not expose her body indiscreetly. She thrashes him in his arms and spits on his face with hatred. She goes to the toilet as a sudden urge to void her bowels seizes her. When she voids it, she feels her body is becoming only an utter body, a good-for-nothing body that digests and excretes. Her soul loses its onlooker's curiosity and retreats deep into her body. Tereza feels a deep impulse to go into him and hear his voice, but resists herself, fearing she may burst into tears. She goes inside, picks up her clothes from the floor, puts them on, and leaves. The engineer, surprisingly, disappears after this incident, leaving in Tereza the apprehension that he must be with the secret police. This incident is intriguing because it leaves the readers with so many doubts: Who is that engineer? What is his motive? Why does he disappear from Tereza's life? If he is with the secret police, what does he want from Tereza? Kundera does not give answers to these questions in the novel. The readers do not see him after this incident; Tereza, however, is not able to forget this incident and lives under the constant fear of being caught by Tomas for her adultery.

The incident at the engineer's flat has an oneiric nature. As noted, it was placed immediately after the Petron Hill incident, a dream series. It is typical of Kundera to enter into and leave the oneiric abruptly yet spontaneously, giving readers no perceptible marks of a transition. The gap between reality and the dream sometimes fuses so well that the audience wonders which is reality and which is a dream. The flat of the engineer has a bizarre, dreamlike structure that strikes Tereza as soon as she enters it; "The entire flat consisted of a single room with a curtain setting off the first five or six feet from the rest and therefore forming a kind of makeshift anteroom" (Kundera 148). The

room has no library, and hundreds of books lie scattered around. This sight relieves anxiety for Tereza, who has liked books since childhood. To her surprise, she sees a translation of Sophocles' *Oedipus*, which reminds her of the article Tomas had sent to a weekly. Though Tereza asks the engineer why he had the copy, whether he had read it, and what he thought about it, he puts his arms around her instead of answering such questions. He returns the copy to the shelf and leads her to the daybed. There, of course, is a rationale behind the inclusion of this episode in the novel because it tells us how miserable Tereza feels about Tomas's compulsive womanizing and his treating all bodies alike. For Tereza, the only way to escape from such disgrace and shame is to betray Tomas, for whom love and sexuality are two different domains, and commitment is never a possibility. The engineer and his flat do not acquire any significance in the novel other than being the cause and the setting for Agnes' infidelity. This episode unfolds so organically in the novel that it does not create any unnaturalness or confusion in the readers about its causality and temporality. The span of this incident is relatively short, just like a dream, but its impact on Tereza's life is devastating. It becomes a nightmare, and Tereza never finds an escape.

Tomas and Tereza finally escape to the countryside in search of an idyll. However, Tereza's oneiric world continues to visit her. Following Karenin, her pet dog's cancer diagnosis, Tereza has a dream wherein "Karenin gave birth to two rolls and a bee. He stared, amazed, at his own progeny. The rolls were utterly serene, but the bee staggered about as if drugged, then flew up and away" (Kundera 282). This is the only dream in Tereza's oneiric, which has a surreal nature and a bizarre setting, and hence, unlike the other dreams, the readers can easily discern that what they are reading is a dream sequence. Unlike the other dreams, whose content is always Tereza's fear and jealousy about Tomas's liaisons, this one corresponds to Tereza's anxieties about her own body and the

feelings of motherhood. The dream also tells us about Tereza's fear of losing Karenin, who has been her sole companion in this world. As always, Tereza shares her dream with Tomas, and they both find a certain relief in it. "It transformed Karenin's illness into pregnancy and the drama of giving birth into something both laughable and touching: two rolls and a bee" (Kundera 283). In Tereza's final dream, which happens just before their tragic death, Tomas is called to an airfield from where Tomas and Tereza are taken on an airplane to a strange place. They see three men holding rifles, and one of them shoots Tomas. To her surprise, Tomas's body shrinks and becomes a tiny rabbit that starts binkying and dashing across the airfield. The man who shot him picks up the tiny creature and gives it over to Tereza. "She was happy to be holding an animal in her arms, happy that the animal was hers and she could press it to her body" (Kundera 297). Tereza takes the rabbit home, feeling that she has finally achieved her goal. This dream, especially its initial part, is so close to reality in many respects. Tomasa and Tereza may have escaped from the city and settled in the countryside. However, the presence of the regime is still felt here. Tomas has been under the regime's radar since he wrote the infamous article on Oedipus. The regime had asked Tomas several times and, in several forms, to retract the article and write a letter of apology. However, he conveniently escaped such threats and eventually settled in the countryside. The readers fear that the agents of the regime could come to them at any time, especially after Tomas and Terza have settled in the countryside. Moreover, this is why the initial part of Tereza's dream feels like a real incident. What happens in the dream has a causal connection to reality. When they go to the airfield and are taken on the airplane, the readers may feel that it may be the agents of the regime who are kidnapping them. The events in the dream look like the continuation of real life. When Tomas becomes a rabbit, and Tereza holds, the readers realize it is yet another dream in Tereza's oneiric world.

Conclusion

The dreams this paper has read show that in Kundera, the two ontological areas, dream and reality, coalesce and are often indistinguishable. More often than not, dreams leak into the real world, blurring the boundaries of the real and the oneiric. Sometimes, dreams begin like the natural progression of the narrative and then tilt into events that have nothing to do with what has been happening in the real world. To understand the flow of narrative, readers do not need to differentiate between the real and the oneiric in Kundera, as they are often coupled and operate in the same universe. Tereza's series of dreams in the novel does not have the so-called dreamlike setting or paraphernalia, nor do they seek a separate realm for their unfolding. They unfold as organically and naturally as an event in real life and have no causality or spatiality intrinsic to them. The content in the oneiric is analogous and contingent upon the events that happen in the real world. By critically reading Tereza's dreams, this paper proves that Kundera's oneiric radically differs from the other novelists and problematizes the absolute and oneiric dichotomies. In Kundera, the oneiric acquires a new dimension and an epistemological meaning. While the real and the oneiric are distinctively different ontological areas for others, Kundera allows them to merge organically and often treats them as inseparably close and connected. In Kundera, the shift or transition from the real to the oneiric or vice versa is often imperceptibly smooth. It does not obstruct the flow of the narrative or cause difficulties in understanding the narrative. As the oneiric and the real converge, Tereza's series of dreams in the novel requires no interpretations as they are aesthetic, an organic part of the narrative, and not coded communications like the dreams in the works of other writers. To enter her oneiric world, one does not need a prerequisite in the Psychoanalytical method, as her dreams and reality are often the same. By using insights from Merleau Ponty, the paper showed how Kundera reassesses the imaginary or unconscious and

succeeds in giving an ontological and epistemological status to the oneiric. Oneiric in Kundera's novels not only opens up the possibility of looking at his characters in a new light and dimension but also prompts a rethinking of how dreams have been experienced and interpreted.

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Bio Note

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Declaration

I, Shybu K P, hereby declare that this paper titled “The Ontological Multiplicities: A Critical Reading of Tereza's Oneiric World in *The Unbearable Lightness of Being*” is an original work and has not been submitted, published, or presented elsewhere in part or whole. I have appropriately acknowledged all sources and references in the paper. I understand that any breach of academic integrity may affect the prospect of publication and result in disciplinary action.